

IMPLEMENTING A CLINICAL DECISION SUPPORT TOOL TO MINIMIZE NITROUS OXIDE USE

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Background

- N₂O is a greenhouse gas that contributes to global warming/climate change & declining public health
- 250,000 deaths by 2030 from effects of global warming
 - N₂O remains non-degraded in the ozone layer the longest:
 - Sevo=1.1 yrs; Iso= 3.2 yrs; Des=14 yrs
 - **N₂O for 114 years**
 - N₂O also increases the global warming potential of Sevo by 590% and Iso by 290%
 - Ranks 3rd in the world for most climatologically significant greenhouse gas
 - Running N₂O for 1 hr is the same as driving a car for:
 - 29 miles @ 0.5 L/min
 - 57 miles @ 1L/min
 - 112 mile @ 2L/min

Purpose

Decrease the long-term use of N₂O in terms of mean L/min flows & mean duration of use in minutes by implementing a CDST pop-up advisory

Goals:

1. Decreased mean L/min N₂O flows
2. Decreased mean duration of N₂O use in minutes

Methods

- **Setting:**
 - KPFC main operating rooms
 - 10 operating rooms
- All practicing anesthesiologists (MDAs) & CRNAs were involved in the pilot.
 - 80 CRNAs & 52 MDAs
- **Sample:**
 - **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Non-obstetric, adult male & female, general anesthesia cases
 - **Exclusion Criteria:**
 - Obstetric, regional, monitored anesthesia care (MAC), and non-OR anesthesia, and pediatrics
- **Data Collection:**
 - **Baseline Data:**
 - Collected from intraoperative records from Oct. 1, 2020 - Mar. 18, 2021 prior to pilot
 - **Post Intervention Data:**
 - Collected through August 2021
- **Go-Live Date:** Mar. 19, 2020

Theoretical Framework: Iowa Model

Results

1,832 encounters included in the analysis from Oct. 1, 2020, to Aug. 30, 2021

Year/Month	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std	N
2020/10	0.11	9	1.38	1.95	1.56	209
2020/11	0.196	8.24	1.27	1.83	1.41	177
2020/12	0.286	7.5	1.41	1.89	1.28	177
2021/1	0.5	7.5	1.32	1.93	1.5	149
2021/2	0.379	7.5	1.37	2.01	1.52	206
2021/3	0.143	9	1.31	1.9	1.48	176
2021/4	0.395	6.66	1.36	1.94	1.48	148
2021/5	0.02	7.57	1.25	1.95	1.59	155
2021/6	0.419	7.5	1.25	1.81	1.55	168
2021/7	0.43	8.6	1.3	2.02	1.69	149
2021/8	0.01	7.1	1.2	1.66	1.23	118

Nitrous Oxide Liter per Minute flow by Month

- No statistically significant difference ($p=0.406$) observed with Welch's two sample t-test pre vs. post intervention
- Marginally significant difference ($p=0.061$) was observed with Wilcoxon rank sum-test with continuity correction for flows prior vs. after intervention.
 - 6.1% chance that differences between pre and post intervention data occurred randomly, and not as a direct result CDST intervention

Year/Month	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std	N
2020/10	3	295	32	50.1	52.8	209
2020/11	2	291	34	56.5	54.9	177
2020/12	2	297	42	58.9	49.7	177
2021/1	3	241	32	51.5	48.4	149
2021/2	2	315	33	54.4	54.1	206
2021/3	1	407	27	52.6	60.3	176
2021/4	5	556	29	55.9	68.8	148
2021/5	2	457	30	53.6	65.5	155
2021/6	2	250	37	48.1	39.1	168
2021/7	6	327	42	58	55	149
2021/8	4	579	37.5	63.4	82.3	118

Nitrous Oxide Use in Duration in Minutes by Month

No statistically significant difference observed for total duration (minutes) prior vs. after intervention with either Welch's t-test ($p=0.333$) or Wilcoxon rank-sum test ($p=0.683$).

Discussion

- Results may suggest extensive outliers skewed the distribution of the data for L/min flow measure. However, overall sustained decrease in raw number of cases utilizing N₂O after March compared to the months prior
- Monthly median flows & duration were consistently less than the mean
 - This suggests there are a select number of providers who consistently use N₂O at higher flows/duration compared to most other providers → skewing data findings & exaggerating overall use of N₂O within the hospital. However, continuous decrease in the number of cases utilizing N₂O was still noted to correlate with the implementation of the CDST

Limitations

Possible Confounders:

- Poster Board
 - Placed concurrently throughout CDST pilot - may have influenced decision-making
- Previous educational intervention conducted by the DNP cohort of 2021
- No control groups
- Did not obtain specific provider or patient identifiers, limiting the ability to analyze causation & correlation of N₂O use throughout pilot
- Using mean data of L/min flow & duration of time may not accurately depict N₂O use trends
 - i.e., a better measure may be the raw number of cases using N₂O

Strengths

- 11 months of data collection
 - Monitor N₂O trends over time
 - Assess sustained practice change
- Less likelihood of sampling bias
 - Data extracted from EMR
 - Captured all anesthetic records based on inclusion and exclusion criteria

Future Implications

- With a larger sample size, or ability to adjust for confounders, this intervention may yield statistically significant results
- Future study needed to investigate cause of outlying data including associated patients, provider characteristics, & provider education deficits
- Individual provider characteristics & qualitative data is recommended to better understand practice habits to determine more effective strategies to influence a change in practice

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